

MATLAB/SIMULINK YORDAMIDA UCH FAZALI ASINXRON MOTORNING DINAMIK MODELI

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Maqolada ixtiyoriy sanoq tizimida stator va rotor o'zgaruvchilarining dq0 o'qida o'zgarishidandan foydalangan holda Matlab/Simulink dasturida asinxron motorning modelini yaratish jarayoni bosqichma-bosqich tushuntirilgan. Dinamik modellar o'tkinchi va barqaror holat sharoitida asinxron motorning ishlashini yaxshiroq tushunish uchun ishlatiladi. Dinamik modellashtirish inersiya, moment va tezlik uchun barcha mexanik tenglamalarni hisobga oladi. Qo'zg'almas stator va harakatlanuvchi rotor o'rtasidagi barcha differensial kuchlanishlar, toklar va magnit oqimlar ham modellashtirilgan.

Статья представляет собой пошаговое объяснение процесса создания модели асинхронной машины в Matlab/Simulink с использованием преобразований оси dq0 переменных статора и ротора в произвольной системе отсчета. Динамические модели используются для того, чтобы лучше понять поведение асинхронного двигателя как в переходном, так и в стационарном состоянии. В динамическом моделировании учитываются все механические уравнения для инерции, крутящего момента и скорости в зависимости от времени. Также моделируются все дифференциальные напряжения, токи и магнитные потоки между неподвижным статором и движущимся ротором.

The article is a step-by-step explanation of the process of creating a model of an asynchronous machine in Matlab/Simulink using dq0 axis transformations of the stator and rotor variables in an arbitrary reference frame. Dynamic models are used to better understand the behavior of an induction motor in both transient and steady-state conditions. Dynamic simulation takes into account all mechanical equations for inertia, torque and speed versus time. All differential voltages, currents and magnetic fluxes between the stationary stator and the moving rotor are also modeled.

Keywords: Matlab/Simulink software, induction motor, dq transformation, modelling, current, torque, speed.

Ключевые слова: программное обеспечение Matlab/Simulink, асинхронный двигатель, преобразование dq, моделирование, ток, крутящий момент, скорость.

Kalit so'zlar: Matlab/Simulink dasturiy ta'minoti, asinxron motor, dq o'zgartirish, modellashtirish, tok, moment, tezlik.

KIRISH Asinxron motorning dinamik holatini tavsiflovchi kuchlanish va aylanuvchi moment tenglamalari vaqt o'tishi bilan o'zgaradi. U differensial tenglamalarni echishda muvaffaqiyatli qo'llaniladi va ba'zi murakkabliklarni o'z

ichiga olishi mumkin. Mashinaning kuchlanish tenglamalaridan nisbiy harakatdagi elektr zanjirlari tufayli barcha vaqt bo'yicha o'zgaruvchan induktivliklarni hisobga olmaslik orqali ushbu tenglamalarning murakkabligini kamaytirish uchun o'zgaruvchilarni almashtirishdan foydalanish mumkin [1, 2]. Ushbu yondashuv bilan ko'p fazali chulg'amni magnit o'qlari kvadratga joylashgan ikki fazali chulg'am (qd) to'plamiga qisqartirilishi mumkin. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, asinxron motorning stator va rotor o'zgaruvchilari (kuchlanishlar, toklar va oqim ilashuvchanliklari) har qanday burchak aylanishi tezligida yoki harakatsiz qolishi mumkin bo'lgan koordinatalar sistemasiga uzatiladi. Bunday koordinatalar sistemasi umumlashgan mashinalarni tahlil qilishda ixtiyoriy koordinatalar sistemasi sifatida ma'lum hisoblanadi [3].

1-rasm. Asinxron motorning dq0 almashtirish sxemasi

Ixtiyoriy koordinatalar sistemasi simmetrik asinxron mashinalarining dinamik tahlili standart modellashtirish yondashuvi sifatida keng qo'llaniladi, u orqali har qanday maxsus ish rejimini loyihalash mumkin. Matlab/Simulink dasturi dq0 o'qqa o'zgartirish orqali foydalanish orqali asinxron motorni modellashtirishda boshqa mashina simulyatorlariga nisbatan afzalliklarga ega

SHunday qilib, model tenglamalari orasidagi har bir individual tenglama bitta blokda osongina amalga oshirilishi mumkin, shunda barcha mashina o'zgaruvchilari nazorat va tekshirish maqsadlarida mavjud bo'lishi mumkin. Ushbu maqolada Matlab/Simulink dasturi yordamida asinxron motorning modelini dinamik xususiyatlarini modellashtirish uchun stator va rotor o'zgaruvchilari koordinatalar sistemasiga keltirilgan [5].

Model tenglamalarini 1-rasmda ko'rsatilgan asinxron elektr motorning dq0 almashtirish sxemasidan hosil qilish mumkin. Ushbu sxema bilan bog'langan oqim ilashuvchanlik tenglamalarini quyidagicha topish mumkin:

$$\psi_{ds} = L_s i_{ds} + L_m i_{dr} \quad (1)$$

$$\psi_{qs} = L_s i_{qs} + L_m i_{qr} \quad (2)$$

$$\psi_{dr} = L_r i_{dr} + L_m i_{ds} \quad (3)$$

$$\psi_{qr} = L_r i_{qr} + L_m i_{qs} \quad (4)$$

SHundan so‘ng, oqim ilashuvchanliklarning qiymatlarini almashtirib, toklarni topamiz:

$$i_{ds} = \frac{L_r}{D} \psi_{ds} - \frac{L_m}{D} \psi_{dr}; \quad (5)$$

$$i_{qs} = \frac{L_r}{D} \psi_{qs} - \frac{L_m}{D} \psi_{qr}; \quad (6)$$

$$i_{dr} = -\frac{L_m}{D} \psi_{ds} + \frac{L_s}{D} \psi_{dr}; \quad (7)$$

$$i_{qr} = -\frac{L_m}{D} \psi_{qs} + \frac{L_s}{D} \psi_{qr}; \quad (8)$$

bu erda

$$D = L_s L_r - L_m^2; \quad (9)$$

Kuchlanishlarni topish uchun quyidagi formulalardan foydalanamiz

$$v_{ds} = R_s i_{ds} + p \psi_{ds} \quad (10)$$

$$v_{qs} = R_s i_{qs} + p \psi_{qs} \quad (11)$$

$$v_{dr} = R_r i_{dr} + p \psi_{dr} + \omega_m \psi_{qr} \quad (12)$$

$$v_{qr} = R_r i_{qr} + p \psi_{qr} + \omega_m \psi_{dr} \quad (13)$$

Yuqoridagi tenglamalarga asoslanib, moment va rotor tezligi quyidagicha aniqlash mumkin:

$$T_e = \frac{3}{2} p I_m (i_{qs} i_{dr} - i_{ds} i_{qr}) \quad (14)$$

$$\omega_r = \int \frac{P}{2J} (T_e - T_L) \quad (15)$$

bu erda, p -qutblar soni; j -inersiya momenti (kg/m^2).

Qisqa tutashgan rotorli asinxron motor uchun magnit oqim tenglamalarida V_{qr} va V_{dr} rotor kuchlanishlari nolga teng, chunki rotor sterjenlari qisqa tutashgan hisoblanadi. dq o‘qdagi oqimlari va stator toklari yordamida moment va tezlik tenglamalarini hisoblagandan so‘ng, dq o‘qqa o‘zgartirish orqali elektr motor (stator) kirish kuchlanishlariga qo‘llanilishi kerak [1, 3].

Muvozanat sharoitida asinxron mashinaning uch fazali stator kuchlanishlari quyidagicha ifodalanishi mumkin:

$$V_a = \sqrt{2} V_{rms} \sin(\omega t) \quad (16)$$

$$V_b = \sqrt{2} V_{rms} \sin(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{3}) \quad (17)$$

$$V_c = \sqrt{2} V_{rms} \sin(\omega t + \frac{2\pi}{3}) \quad (18)$$

Ushbu uch fazali kuchlanishlar sinxron aylanadigan mos koordinatalar tizimiga faqat ikki fazada uzatiladi (dq o‘qqa o‘zgartirish). Buni quyidagi ikkita tenglama yordamida amalga oshirish mumkin:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_\alpha \\ V_\beta \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1/2 & -1/2 \\ 0 & \sqrt{3}/2 & -\sqrt{3}/2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_a \\ V_b \\ V_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

U holda to‘g‘ri va kvadrat o‘qlar bo‘ylab kuchlanishlar quyidagiga teng bo‘ladi:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_d \\ V_q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_\alpha \\ V_\beta \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

Uch fazali tizimdagi stator va rotor toklarining oniy qiymatlari natijada quyidagi o‘zgartirish yordamida hisoblanadi:

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_\alpha \\ i_\beta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & -\sin \theta \\ \sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_d \\ i_q \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ -1/2 & -\sqrt{3}/2 \\ -1/2 & \sqrt{3}/2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_\alpha \\ i_\beta \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

Matlab/Simulink yordamida uch fazali asinxron motor modeli modellashtirildi. Model yuqorida keltirilgan tenglamalar to‘plami yordamida amalga oshiriladi. 2-rasmda tasvirlangan asinxron motor modelining to‘liq Simulink sxemasi ko‘rsatilgan.

Ushbu modelda yordamida uch fazali stator kuchlanishlarini modellashtirish tenglamalar (16, 17, 18) bo‘yicha ishlab chiqarishdan boshlanadi, shundan so‘ng ushbu muvozanatlangan kuchlanishlarni (19, 20) tenglamalarda bo‘lgani kabi Klark va Park o‘zgartirishidan foydalangan holda sinxron aylanadigan ramka bilan bog‘liq ikki fazali kuchlanishlarga o‘zgartiriladi. SHundan so‘ng, quyida ko‘rsatilganidek, dq oqim ilashuvchanlik va tok tenglamalari amalga oshirildi. (1)-(4) tenglamalarda ko‘rsatilgan Ψ_{ds} , Ψ_{qs} , Ψ_{dr} , Ψ_{qr} oqim ilashuvchanliklarni foydalanilgan holda Matlab/Simulink modelini tuzish mumkin.

2-rasm. Uch fazali asinxron motorning Matlab/Simulink modeli
 3-rasmda (5) - (9) tenglamalarga muvofiq i_{qs} , i_{ds} , i_{qr} , i_{dr} toklarni hisoblash uchun ishlatiladigan Simulink bloklari ko‘rsatilgan.

3-rasm. dq tok tenglamalarini amalga oshirish

Ushbu model yordamida quvvati 0,75 kVt bo‘lgan asinxron motor sinovdan o‘tkazildi. Modellashtirish natijalari quyidagi xususiyatlarga ega asinxron motor uchun berilgan: $U=230$ V, $2p=4$, $f=50$ Hz; $R_s=15.7$ Om, $R_r=8.4$ Om, $L_{ls}=0.005$ Gn, $L_{lr}=0.025$ Gn, $L_m=0.61$ Gn, $J=0.017$ kg/m², $T_e=5.1$ Nm. Asinxron motorning turli xil ish xususiyatlari iste‘mol qiladigan elektromagnit moment, rotorning aylanish tezligi va statorning uchta faza chulg‘amlaridagi toklarni vaqt bo‘yicha o‘zgarish grafiklari olindi (4÷6-rasmlar).

4-rasm. A, B va C fazalarda stator toklari

5-rasm. Elektromagnit moment

**6-rasm. Rotorning aylanish tezligi
XULOSA**

Ushbu maqolada Matlab/Simulink yordamida uch fazali asinxron motorning dinamik modeli ishlab chiqilgan. Model yordamida quvvati 0.75 kVt bo‘lgan asinxron motor bilan sinovdan o‘tkazildi. Imitatsiya qilingan motorning moment va tezlik xarakteristikalari bo‘yicha qoniqarli javob berdi. Matlab/Simulink sanoq tizimi nazariyasidan foydalangan holda asinxron motorlarning ishini tahlil qilish, shuningdek bashorat qilishning ishonchli va murakkab usuli hisoblanadi.

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